

Energy Consumption Modeling by Machine Learning from Daily Activity Metering in a Hospital

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Abstract

Hospitals are large buildings that consume a great amount of energy mostly due to their continuous energy consumption needs, high consumer medical equipment, and special requirements of thermal and air conditions. Reliable dynamic simulation is a chimera because of the complex design and behavior of these buildings. Therefore, monitoring-based methods arise as a plausible alternative. Its main drawback, however, is the lack of enough data to generate statistically robust models.

The paper faces this problem thanks to the helpful contribution of a collaborative hospital which was able to generate daily data of electrical energy consumption for a period of six years. Besides, thirteen variables that summarize the daily activity of the hospital are also included. The results show how machine learning techniques generate models that accurately predict the electrical energy consumption based on weather conditions and activity measurements.

The obtained results are useful for the design of more specific energy saving strategies, a more efficient economic investment for energy retrofitting of existing buildings and a better management of economic energy cost in large-scale buildings.

1 Introduction

In Europe, buildings represent more than one third of total energy consumption [1]. Nowadays, the state members are far from the 2020 energy targets: 20% improvement in the European Union energy efficiency and 20% reduction in EU greenhouse gas emissions [2]. A great effort has been made in promoting energy efficiency in new buildings. However, given the average age of building

stock in the European countries, a major contribution must be made by energy retrofitting of existing buildings.

Energy consumption forecasting provides valuable information for: a) evaluating consumption profiles, b) detecting energy saving opportunities, and c) designing energy efficiency measures in existing buildings [3]. Knowledge of building energy demand profiles is an integral step in the design of energy saving initiatives. Deeper knowledge of demand profiles guarantees higher accuracy of saving measures and the success of energy efficiency initiatives in existing buildings. In this sense, a great effort has been made in modeling and energy forecast for small-medium buildings, especially residential ones. However, an existing gap is still observed for large energy consuming buildings, such as Large Medical Centers.

Hospitals represent the highest rates of energy consumption per unit floor area in the building sector [4]. Large Medical Centers have specific features which clearly distinguish them from other kinds of buildings and difficult the energy modeling tasks: 1) a continuous energy and electricity utilization is required; 2) difficulties in measuring detailed building occupancy; 3) complex and energy-intensive facilities (surgeries rooms, TAC machines) are usually subject to unpredictable events; and 4) restrictive requirements of air quality and indoor comfort temperature. Besides, any energy saving initiatives must preserve healthcare delivery [3, 5, 6].

Different modeling approaches are available for building energy forecasting. Depending on the availability and detail of data, each one has advantages and limitations: 1) dynamic models are based on solving mathematical equations derived from physical laws and require high detailed information of building materials; 2) bill-based methods requires less information but offer short options for innovation; 3) statistical methods do not require detailed information from the building and rely on training data to extract system function. For building energy forecasting, multiple regression, artificial neural networks (ANNs) and decision trees are the most used statistical techniques [7].

There are few studies that use predictive models for energy consumption forecasting in medical centers. In [3], it is used a multi-layer perceptron ANN, based on a backpropagation algorithm, to predict energy consumption in a large hospital facility. The authors grouped into seasonal subsets yearly data in order to reduce forecast errors. Chen et al. [8] used ANN for predicting hospital air-conditioner electricity. The researchers adopted occupancy as the internal variable and temperature and moisture as external variables.

The present work proposes a load forecasting methodology for an existing hospital. A set of machine learning techniques are applied in this research to obtain models from data that represent the dynamic of the hospital. The work aims at designing predictive models that allow the experts to forecast energy consumption (dependent variables) provided we know some variables about date, weather, activity, and occupancy (independent variables). These models can be useful to estimate future consumptions, analyze the sensitivity of the variables, study different scenarios and profiles, etc. In machine learning, this approach falls within the so-called supervised learning. Within predictive approaches,

this work focuses on regression, which obtains models able to approximate the estimated continuous output as close as possible to the real continuous output from a set of input variables.

In general, this data can be obtained by measuring different real building dynamics. We distinguish among different kinds of data: 1) data about time, date, weekday, and holiday; 2) data about outdoor weather condition such as temperature, humidity, radiation, or wind; 3) data about activity of the hospital such as admissions, discharges, revisions, first consults, emergencies, medical day sessions, surgical interventions, or medical tests; 4) data about occupancy of the hospital such as staff size or number of visitors; 5) data about energy consumption by fuel (electrical, gas or petrol). The present study uses some representative variables of these different groups. The data can be represented by different type of variables: nominal/categorical, ordinal, Boolean, continuous, etc. Some machine learning techniques are limited to some of these types so sometimes it is necessary to perform different data transformation tasks. The resolution of the data, i.e., the period of data sampling, is typically monthly, daily, or hourly. For a successful use of machine learning techniques, a fine resolution is required, being recommended at least daily data.

For the sake of performing an alternative analysis with modeling techniques different to the ones used in other hospitals to predict energy consumption, a great effort was made in Hospital San Cecilio (Granada, Spain) to obtain daily data that would allow applying data-driven modeling approaches based on machine learning as performed in the present research.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 show the available data and apply some visualizations to analyze it in a general way. Section 3 establishes the experimental methodology followed in this study. Section 4 introduces the used machine learning techniques and presents the obtained results with different set of variables. Section 5 discusses the main ideas extracted from the experimental results. Finally, Section 6 concludes with a summary of the performed research and some future works.

2 Data Exploratory Analysis

We were able to obtain daily data about electrical energy consumption as well as 13 activity variables for the period between January 1, 2010 and December 31, 2015 (6 years). Therefore, a total of 2,191 data are used. Data about daily minimum, average, and maximum outside air temperatures are also gathered per day. Before applying the machine learning algorithms, a brief analysis is performed in order to better understand the available data. Table 1 and Figure 1 show the electrical energy consumption (kWh) and average outside temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the period 2010-2015. In this figure, the electrical energy consumption is shown as the average daily value computed for each month so we can see a plot similar to the case where only monthly data would be available.

There is a clear correlation between electrical energy consumption and temperature in most of the months but it does not seem to exist a direct correlation

Table 1: Monthly average temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)—upper row—and electrical energy consumption per day (kWh)—lower row—for six years (2010-2015)

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Avg.
2010	6.2	7.7	9.5	13.8	16.0	20.6	26.1	25.4	20.0	13.8	7.9	7.2	14.5
	16336	17039	15832	14804	15505	19316	25404	24202	19173	15808	16797	16618	18069.5
2011	6.8	8.0	10.7	16.4	19.3	23.9	26.3	26.7	22.7	17.5	11.4	6.6	16.4
	16520	17218	16420	14866	15753	20822	23662	23569	19352	16518	16462	16744	18159.0
2012	5.0	4.3	10.6	11.8	19.1	24.4	25.7	25.9	20.2	15.6	11.1	7.2	15.1
	17555	18068	16127	15284	17750	22506	23232	24116	18872	15803	15609	15713	18386.4
2013	6.6	6.9	10.5	13.9	16.4	21.9	26.1	26.7	21.6	17.5	8.7	6.6	15.3
	16529	16921	15816	15696	15448	18244	23225	23080	17733	16124	15635	16120	17547.5
2014	7.7	8.5	11.3	16.5	19.8	23.1	26.3	26.0	22.0	17.3	11.7	5.2	16.3
	16667	16838	15553	15011	16352	18625	23024	22370	19105	15472	15451	15886	17529.5
2015	4.8	6.4	11.2	15.4	20.6	23.4	28.8	26.5	20.3	16.5	10.8	8.2	16.1
	16703	17103	15322	14526	16875	19554	27456	23047	17134	14403	14886	15036	17670.3
Avg.	6.2	7.0	10.6	14.7	18.5	22.9	26.6	26.2	21.2	16.4	10.3	6.8	15.6
	16718	17198	15845	15031	16281	19844	24334	23397	18561	15688	15807	16020	17893.7

Figure 1: Monthly data of electrical energy consumption per day and average temperature (2010-2015). Shaded areas indicate the periods where the two variables are not directly correlated

Figure 2: Daily data of average temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and electrical energy consumption (kWh) in 2015. Monthly data are also shown with dashed lines

in cold months (usually from November to mid-March) as highlighted in the shaded areas of Figure 1. These periods differ slightly depending on the year, but similar patterns are found. The reason of this behavior may be related with the installation of this old hospital. The cooling is performed by split-type air conditioners (about 1,300 units) spread out the building that were installed during the 1990s and early 2000s. Most of these units have also heat pumps so the users of the hospital switch on them in winter to reinforce the petrol-based heating system.

Figure 2 shows the daily data to get further insight into the behavior of electrical energy consumption with respect to average temperature. We can observe there is an important noise on the signal with strong changes of temperature in short periods of a few days and so the electrical energy consumption. It is also observable the periodic oscillation of electrical energy consumption per week, as hospital activity is notably reduced in weekends. This figure makes clear how much information we are losing when analyzing monthly data and, therefore, the convenience of using daily data for getting more accurate and useful models.

3 Testing Methodology with Data-Driven Machine Learning Techniques for Regression

3.1 Experimental setup in predictive approaches

It is necessary to define a model validation technique for assessing how the results of an obtained model will generalize to an independent data set. In other words, we want to estimate how accurately a predictive model will perform in practice. To do so, the data set is divided into two subsets: training and test data sets. The training one is provided to the machine learning algorithm in order to generate the predictive model. The test one, which contains data never seen by the learning algorithm, is used to validate the performance of the model.

There are different techniques to randomly form these training and test data sets. In this paper, we will use the cross validation technique (one of the most frequently used in machine learning) with 10 folds. This procedure consists on randomly separating the data set into ten disjoint subsets. Then, ten experiments are performed by using nine of these subsets to train the considered machine-learning algorithm. The obtained model is then tested on the tenth subset (which was not used for training) to analyze its prediction capability. Average results on these ten tests are shown for each algorithm. The same random data partition must be used for all the analyzed algorithms and studies.

3.2 Performance metrics

Different metrics are used to assess the quality of the models obtained by machine learning. These functions are deeply related to the performed learning task. In regression, the performance of the model is related to the similarity between the predicted (\hat{y}_i) and the real (y_i) values (with $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and n being the data set size). Different functions can be considered, being the most usual as follows:

- R^2 (coefficient of determination): it indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variable. It returns a value between 0 and 1, being better the closer it is to 1.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}, \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i$$

- MAE (mean absolute error): it is an average of the errors committed in each prediction. It returns a non-negative value in the same scale as the predicted data, being better the closer it is to 0.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|$$

- MSD (mean signed deviation): it is the average of the differences between predicted and real values. It returns a value in the same scale that the

predicted data, being better the closer it is to 0. A negative MSD means that the regressor tends to underestimate the variable, while positive MSD means it overestimates the variable.

$$MSD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{y}_i - y_i$$

- MSE (mean squared error): it measures the average of the squares of the errors. Contrary to MAE, MSE incorporates not only the bias, but also the variance. It returns a non-negative value in the scale of the square of the predicted data, being better the closer it is to 0.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2$$

- RMSE (root-mean-square error): it is the root of MSE. It has the advantage of returning a non-negative value in the same scale that the predicted data; it is better the closer it is to 0.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{n}}$$

- Additionally, in this research we found useful an additional measure that explains the average bias between predicted and real value in relative terms. Final users can more easily understand this measure. It returns the mean percentage error (MPE) as follows:

$$MPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n PE_i,$$

$$\text{with } PE_i = \begin{cases} 100 \cdot \left| \frac{\hat{y}_i}{y_i} - 1 \right|, & \text{if } \hat{y}_i > y_i \\ 100 \cdot \left| 1 - \frac{\hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right|, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Standard deviation, percentiles values and box plots of PE can be also reported for a better understanding of the error distribution.

4 Prediction by Different Regression Algorithms

4.1 Machine learning algorithms

Machine learning techniques as support vector machines (SVM) or ANNs derive models impossible to be understood by humans, so these models can be useful to simulate behaviors (e.g. for annual projections, set budgets, predict energy demand...) but they can not explain the reasoning behind them. Conversely,

techniques that generate decision trees or rule sets (usually by greedy or genetic algorithms) can be easily understood so they can help better to analyze the most influent variables and the causality relationships. In between we have solutions as regressions or graphical models, which can be interpreted in a general way. Therefore, it is advisable to apply different machine learning techniques to the same problem and data in order to generate accurate but illegible models (for prediction) as well as more easily interpretable but less accurate ones (for description). Taking these aspects into account, we have chosen three different approaches that provide different interpretability vs. accuracy balances:

- Multilayer perceptron (MLP) [9]: this ANN is a classical approach for regression. It is characterized by obtaining a good accuracy (though there is a risk of overfitting, i.e., strong difference between training and test performance), but the model is illegible at all. A hidden layer with 10 neurons is used, 200 iterations over the training data set are applied.
- M5Rules algorithm [10]: This method performs a separation of the input space based on interval rules (sorted as a decision list) and then a local lineal correlation is applied. The obtained model shows a good legibility with a good prediction accuracy. As the model can be interpreted, the expert may understand the reasoning behind it, which can be helpful for improving decision-making tasks. A minimum number of 4 instances are allowed at each leaf node.
- Tree ensemble learner (TEL) algorithm [11]: This family of methods (also known as Random Forest) are showing very accurate results in different problems in the last years, thus being considered as the state-of-the-art in machine learning. We will use a version based on multiple decision regression trees with bagging and boosting approaches to generate diverse models that will improve aggregate performance. These methods provide an excellent accuracy but poor interpretability (just a general study of the influence of the input variables is carried out). A total of 300 models are used.

The chosen algorithms and parameter settings can be tuned for a better behavior. This work does not intend to perform an exhaustive experiment but just showing the potential of machine learning on predicting energy consumption in large buildings.

4.2 Experimental results

4.2.1 Study 1—Daily data of temperature vs. electrical energy (EE) consumption

In this first study we will consider exclusively the outside air temperature (minimum, average, and maximum per day) in Celsius degrees to predict the daily electrical energy (EE) consumption in kWh. Table 2 shows the average results on test data sets with the performance metrics introduced in Section 3.2.

Table 2: Results on Daily Temperature vs. Electrical Energy Consumption (kWh)

	R ²	MAE	MSD	MSE	RMSE
Multilayer perceptron	0.6614	1892	-37.896	5147089	2269
M5Rules	0.6885	1823	4.860	4734738	2176
Tree ensemble learner	0.6558	1890	-17.453	5232707	2288

Table 3: Results on Daily HDD and CDD vs. Electrical Energy Consumption (kWh)

	R ²	MAE	MSD	MSE	RMSE
Multilayer perceptron	0.6735	1849	-2.123	4962410	2228
M5Rules	0.6713	1854	-1.462	4996823	2235
Tree ensemble learner	0.6529	1904	-3.068	5276030	2297

As HDD (heating degree day) and CDD (cooling degree day) is traditionally used in the energy efficiency field because of their capability to express climate stringency, we have also tested the algorithms with other data set that used these two variables instead the three raw temperature variables above mentioned. Enhanced Met Office Method is used based on the real daily average temperature (not the approximation based on maximum and minimum). In HDD, 15°C is used as threshold temperature (Tbase) and minimum daily temperature (Tmin). In CDD, 26°C is used as Tbase and maximum daily temperature (Tmax). The obtained results are collected in Table 3.

From these results we can conclude the daily electrical energy consumption can not be successfully predicted exclusively from temperature variables as the three methods are unable to provide accurate enough solutions.

4.2.2 Study 2—Daily data of temperature and date type vs. electrical energy consumption

In Section 2 we observed there is a weekly periodical component on the electrical energy consumption that was discovered when daily data are analyzed but goes unnoticed when monthly data are considered. It is due to the decrease in the activity of the hospital in the weekends and holidays, which significantly reduces occupancy and services, and hence energy demands. Therefore, we have added three new variables to the data used in study 1: weekday (from Monday to Sunday), weekend (that takes value 1 if it is Saturday or Sunday, or 0 otherwise), and holiday (that takes value 1 if it is one of the 14 holidays per year in Granada, or 0 otherwise). The new results including this additional information is shown in Table 4. The obtained results, much more accurate than before, evidence the importance of the date to estimate electrical energy consumption.

Table 4: Results on Daily Temperature and Date Type vs. Electrical Energy Consumption (kWh)

	R ²	MAE	MSD	MSE	RMSE
Multilayer perceptron	0.8981	932	-13.725	1549523	1245
M5Rules	0.9129	838	-20.564	1323959	1151
Tree ensemble learner	0.9140	837	3.344	1307519	1143

Table 5: Results on Daily HDD, CDD and Date vs. Electrical Energy Consumption (kWh)

	R ²	MAE	MSD	MSE	RMSE
Multilayer perceptron	0.8989	904	-0.878	1537127	1240
M5Rules	0.8912	938	-7.949	1653503	1286
Tree ensemble learner	0.8902	951	2.198	1668381	1292

Table 6: Results on Daily Temperature, Date Type and Activity vs. Electrical Energy Consumption (kWh)

	R ²	MAE	MSD	MSE	RMSE
Multilayer perceptron	0.9015	901	6.583	1496656	1223
M5Rules	0.9330	730	-24.606	1017731	1009
Tree ensemble learner	0.9434	666	-5.642	860797	928

Table 5 shows the results when using HDD and CDD instead raw temperature. As we can observe, the accuracy is lower. This is because the machine learning algorithms are able to internally find the relationships among these variables without the loss of information made when using HDD and CDD, thus being able to squeeze better the available data. Therefore, daily minimum, average and maximum outside air temperatures are considered hereinafter.

4.2.3 Study 3—Daily data of temperature, date type and activity vs. electrical energy consumption

Finally, we have added 13 additional variables that represent different daily activities of the hospital: admissions, discharges, revisions, first consults, available beds, stays, occupation, emergencies, medical day sessions, surgical intervention, nuclear medicine tests, radiology tests, and other tests. The intention is to provide additional information related to occupancy and the use of machinery with high power consumption. Table 6 shows the obtained results.

The prediction accuracy achieved in this last study is really good. With the most accurate model (the one generated by ensemble learning) we are able to

Figure 3: Box plot of the error (in percentage) of the electrical energy consumption prediction per day by the models generated by Tree Ensemble Learning on data with temperature, date type and activity. Center line shows the median; box limits indicate the 25th and 75th percentiles; whiskers extend 1.5 times the interquartile range from the 25th and 75th percentiles, outliers are represented by dots. Mean percentage error (MPE): 3.8%

predict the daily electrical energy consumption with an average error (MPE) of 3.8%, being 75% of the days with an error lower or equal to 5% (see Figure 3). There are, however, some few days where the error is notable (outliers in the box plot); a further analysis of these cases is necessary.

In Figure 4 we can see the good prediction performed by the model generated with this ensemble learning algorithm. As shown, the error is usually higher on the peaks of electrical energy consumption. Figure 5 shows the daily real consumption vs. the predicted one made by this method. Finally, Figure 6 compares real and predicted average electrical energy consumed by the hospital per month. From this figure, we observe that the months with greater underestimation are February (with an error of 2.7%) and July (2.6%) while the overestimation is mainly in April (3.8%) and May (2%). The mean error in monthly predictions is only 1.5%.

Figure 4: Daily real vs. predicted electrical energy consumption (kWh) in 2015

5 Discussion

Through the experiments carried out in the previous sections, we have been able to show the highly accurate predictions attained by machine learning when dealing with daily data for a period of 6 years (an average error of 3.8% in daily predictions and 1.5% in monthly predictions). The study evidences the advantage of using information about the activity of the hospital additionally to the outdoor temperature measurements. In any case, as we can observe, even when there is an improvement on the prediction accuracy compared with only considering type of date (workday, weekend or holiday), it is not as important as expected. The reasons may be twofold:

- on the one hand, the performance obtained by just using date type (workday vs. weekend/holiday) was good as it indirectly includes information about activity (most of services run only in workdays);
- on the other, the information about electrical energy consumption is global for the whole building, while the different analyzed activities (emergency, medical tests, surgical interventions, etc.) are located in different localizations.

From these experiments we can conclude that data type can be a good predictor of the activity and so we can use it in the absence of more detailed daily activity information (something, by the way, that involves a great effort

Figure 5: Predictions of the regression models obtained by ensemble learning for daily electrical energy consumption in the period 2010-2015 from outside air temperature, date type and activity data (R^2 : 0.9434, MAE: 666 kWh, RMSE: 928 kWh, MPE: 3.8%)

Figure 6: Comparison between real and predicted energy consumption (kWh) per month (average results of the six years)

and is expensive to obtain). We believe that this activity information would be much more useful if electrical energy consumption would be disaggregated by areas.

The results of the exposed methodology allow to predict in detail the energy demand as well as identify and quantify independent variables that effect the energy consumption, such as occupancy, activity and events. From this information, it is possible to design specific strategies oriented to each variable in order to save energy and reduce energy demand in existing large-scale buildings. A more accurate design of these strategies involves a more efficient energy investment of public bodies in existing buildings. The methodology exposed in this paper is also useful to forecast energy demand peaks and the associated cause in order to reduce the frequency of these peaks and anticipate to them.

A deeper knowledge on the energy demand distribution is vital for the design and sizing of system for the production and use of renewable energy and/or mixed generation such as co-generation or tri-generation. In terms of economic management, the obtained information is also useful for a detailed study and definition of the most appropriate energy tariff as well as more accurate economic expenses on energy bills. Given the age of the existing building stock in European countries (and specifically in large-scale medical centers), this methodology provides basic information for the design of efficient energy retrofits of existing buildings.

6 Conclusion

In this work we have analyzed the use of different machine learning techniques to predict electrical energy consumption in a hospital of Granada (Spain). A

real-world dataset has been generated with daily measurements of electrical energy consumption, outdoor temperature (min, max and mean), date, and 13 additional variables about the daily activity of the hospital in its different areas. Accurate predicting models has been obtained with an average daily error of 3.8%. From the experiments we conclude that raw temperature values are better predictors than HDD and CDD and that date type (workday vs. weekend/holiday) is also a valuable predictor to improve the accuracy.

As future work, we plan to include more weather condition variables (humidity, radiation, wind. . .) to analyze their influence on predicting energy consumption, to study also the petrol consumption, to develop a deeper analysis of the reasoning behind the obtained models in order to interpret the relationships among the variables and extract useful knowledge for a better understanding, and to apply unsupervised learning approaches in order to segment the input conditions and discover interesting associations that explain specific patterns of energy consumption.

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